

Synthesis of 1,2-bis(4-chloro)acetophenone oxime ethyl ether as a carrier and its application for construction of a new ytterbium(III)-PVC membrane sensor

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Abstract : The new ytterbium(III)-PVC membrane, containing 1,2-bis(4-chloro)acetophenone oxime ethyl ether (AOEE) as an ion carrier, showed a Nernstian response for the Yb^{3+} ions over a wide dynamic linear range between 1.0×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-2} M. The detection limit is 6.3×10^{-7} M while the sensor presents a response time of ~ 7 s and a useful working pH range of 2.6–7.8. The electrode revealed high selectivity with respect to all the common alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions, including the members of the lanthanide family other than Yb^{3+} . The sensor was successfully applied as an indicator electrode in a potentiometric titration of Yb^{III} ions with EDTA. The membrane sensor was used for the recovery of Yb^{3+} ions spiked in tap and river water samples. The proposed sensor was also used for the determination of ytterbium ions concentration mixtures of different ions.

Keywords : Ion-selective electrode, PVC membrane, potentiometry, sensor.

Introduction

Potentiometric sensors have been shown to be very effective tools for analysis of a wide variety of cations and anions. They are very simple to use, inexpensive, and capable of reliable responses in a wide concentration range. A wide variety of chemically, clinically or environmentally important analytes are now routinely monitored using ion-selective sensors based on impregnated polymeric membranes¹⁻³.

Ytterbium is applied to numerous fiber amplifier and fiber optic technologies and in various lasing applications. Ytterbium metal increases its electrical resistance when subjected to very high stresses. All compounds of ytterbium should be treated as highly toxic although initial studies appear to indicate that the danger is limited^{4,5}. Many techniques have been developed for low-level determination of rare-earth ions in solutions such as : spectrophotometry, inductively coupled plasma-MS, inductively coupled plasma-AES, chromatography, electrochemistry, resonance light scattering, isotope dilution mass spectrometry, neutron activation analysis, and X-ray fluorescence spectrometry. Almost all of these techniques are very expensive and time consuming. Potentiometric mem-

brane sensors have shown to be very effective tools for analysis of a wide variety of metal ions. They are very simple, fast, inexpensive, and capable of reliable response in wide concentration ranges.

Recently, we have reported several greatly selective and sensitive PVC-membrane ion selective electrodes for various metal⁶⁻³². There are only a limited number of reports on the development of Yb^{3+} membrane sensors based on different ion carriers in the literature³³⁻³⁵. In this work focuses on the introduction of a highly ytterbium(III)-selective sensor based on 1,2-bis(4-chloro)acetophenone oxime ethyl ether (AOEE) (Fig. 1), as an neutral ionophore for monitoring ytterbium concentration in solution samples.

Fig. 1. Structure of AOEE.

Experimental

Apparatus and materials :

A corning ion analyzer 250 pH//mV meter was used for the potential measurements at 25.0 ± 0.1 °C. Reagent grade dibutyl phthalate (DBP), nitrobenzene (NB), benzyl acetate (BA), acetophenone (AP), sodium tetraphenyl borate (NaTPB), tetrahydrofuran (THF) and high relative molecular weight PVC were purchased from Merck and Aldrich, used as received. The nitrate and chloride salts of all cations used (all from Merck and Aldrich) were of the highest purity available and used without any further purification except for vacuum drying over P_2O_5 . Doubly distilled de-ionized water was used throughout the experiment.

Synthesis of AOEE :

A mixture of 4-chloro acetophenone oxime (0.005 mol) and sodium hydroxide (2.50 g) in solution of the DMSO/ H_2O (5 : 1) 25 mL, was added 1,2-dibromo ethane (0.006 mol) dropwise at room temperature. Then the reaction mixture was stirred for 1.5 h after this time, the residue solid material was filtrated and washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol to produce pure 1,2-bis(4-chloro)acetophenone oxime ethyl ether. Yield : 45% (Found : C, 59.07; H, 4.93; N, 7.48; S, 11.48. $C_{18}H_{18}Cl_2N_2O_2$ requires : C, 59.19; H, 4.97; N, 7.67%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3036, 1552, 1436, 1323 cm^{-1} ; δ_H (ppm) ($CDCl_3$): 2.25 (6H, s, $2CH_3$), 4.51 (4H, s, $2CH_2$) 7.32–7.73 (8H, dd, $2C_6H_4$); MS (m/z) : M^+ , 364 (100%), $(M+2)^+$, 366 (64%).

Membrane preparation :

Membrane solutions were prepared by thoroughly dissolving 2 mg of the AOEE ionophore, 30 mg of powdered PVC, 2 mg of additive NaTPB and 66 mg of plasticizer NB in 3 mL of THF. The resulting mixture was transferred into a glass dish of 2 cm in diameter. The solvent was then evaporated slowly, until an oily, concentrated mixture was obtained. A Pyrex tube (3–5 mm in top) was dipped into the oily mixture for about 5 s, so that a transparent film of about 0.3 mm thickness was formed^{36–48}. The tube was then pulled out from the mix-

ture and kept at the room temperature for about 12 h. Eventually the tube was filled with the internal filling solution (1.0×10^{-3} M ytterbium chloride). The electrode was finally conditioned for 12 h by soaking in a (1.0×10^{-3} M) solution of $YbCl_3$. A silver-silver chloride electrode was used as an internal reference electrode.

The measurements of EMF :

All electromotive force (emf) measurements were carried out with the following cell assembly : Ag/AgCl | internal solution, (1×10^{-3} M $YbCl_3$) | PVC membrane | test solution | Hg_2Cl_2 , KCl (saturated). Activities were calculated according to Debye-Huckel procedure.

Results and discussion

The potential responses of the electrode :

Due to the existence of the donating atoms in the AOEE structure, in the primary experiments, it was used as potentially suitable neutral ion carrier in the fabrication of a number of PVC-membrane ion selective electrodes for Yb^{III} ion and common mono-, di- and trivalent metal ions. Among the examined metal ions, only the resulting Yb^{III} -selective sensor possesses a Nernstian behavior over a very wide concentration range. This is likely due to the high selectivity of AOEE for Yb^{III} ion and the rapid exchange kinetics of the resulting Yb^{3+} -AOEE complex.

The membrane composition effect :

The membrane ingredients, the nature of the solvent mediator and the used additive are the important characteristics of a polymeric membrane sensor. The incorporation of lipophilic anions into the cation-selective membrane electrode not only diminished the ohmic resistance and enhanced the response behavior and selectivity but also, if facing poor extraction capability, it increased the sensitivity of the membrane electrodes^{49–55}. Therefore, the influences of the membrane composition on the potential responses of the Yb^{III} sensor were investigated and the results are summarized in Table 1. As it is seen, the best sensitivity is achieved when the amount of ion-carrier increases up to a value of 2% in the presence of

Table 1. Optimization of membrane ingredients

Electrode No.	Composition (wt%)				Slope (mV/decade)	Linear range (M)
	AOEE	NaTPB	Plasticizer	PVC		
1	2	2	NB, 66	30	20.3 ± 0.2	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
2	1	2	NB, 67	30	16.6 ± 0.4	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
3	3	2	NB, 65	30	18.3 ± 0.5	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
4	2	0	NB, 68	30	12.4 ± 0.3	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ –1.0 × 10 ⁻³
5	2	1	NB, 67	30	17.3 ± 0.2	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
6	2	3	NB, 65	30	18.2 ± 0.4	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
7	2	2	BA, 66	30	16.1 ± 0.3	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
8	2	2	AP, 66	30	17.6 ± 0.6	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
9	2	2	DBP, 66	30	15.5 ± 0.2	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²

2% NaTPB and 66% of polar solvent (NB). Among the four solvent mediators (AP, NB, DBP, and BA) used, the membrane containing NB (membrane no. 6) exhibits a Nernstian response. This is caused by the ability of NB to extract Yb^{III} ions with high charge density from the aqueous phase to the organic membrane phase.

Calibration curve :

The optimum equilibrium time for the membrane electrode, in the presence of 1.0 × 10⁻² M YbCl₃, was 12 h, after which it would generate stable potentials in contact with ytterbium solutions. The electrode shows a linear response to the activity of YbCl₃ ions in the range of 1.0 × 10⁻⁶ to 1.0 × 10⁻² M (Fig. 4). The slope of the calibration graph was 20.3 ± 0.2 mV per decade. The limit of detection, as determined from the intersection of the two extrapolated segments of the calibration graph, was 6.3 × 10⁻⁷ M.

pH effect :

The pH dependence on the membrane electrode was tested over a pH range of 1.0–11.0 at ytterbium ion concentrations (1.0 × 10⁻³ M). The potential was found to remain fairly constant in the range 2.6–7.8 (Fig. 4) (pH adjustment was performed with HCl or NaOH). Beyond this range, a gradual potential drift was observed. The observed decreased potential drift at higher pH values could be attributed to the formation of some Yb^{III} hydroxyl complexes in the solution. At lower pH values, the potential increased, indicating that the membrane sensor responds to hydrogen ions.

Fig. 2. Calibration curve of the Yb³⁺ sensor.

Response time :

In this study, the practical response time of the sensor was recorded by changing the solution with different Yb³⁺ concentrations from 1.0 × 10⁻⁶ to 1.0 × 10⁻² M. The actual potential versus time trace for the electrode based on AOEE is shown in Fig. 3. As it can be seen, the electrode reaches its equilibrium response in a short time of about ~7 s.

Selectivity of the sensor :

Potentiometric selectivity coefficients, describing the AOEE-based membrane sensor for lanthanum ions (A) relative to an interfering ion (B), were determined by the matched potential method^{56–60}. According to the MPM a specified activity (concentration) of primary ions (A) is

Fig. 3. The effect of pH of the test solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ of Yb^{3+}) on the potential response of the ytterbium sensor.

Fig. 4. Dynamic response time of the AOEE membrane sensor for step-wise changes in concentration of Yb^{3+} : (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-6} M$, (B) $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, (C) $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, (D) $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, (E) $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, (F) $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$.

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients of the electrode

M^{n+}	$K_{Yb^{3+},B}^{MPM}$	M^{n+}	$K_{Yb^{3+},B}^{MPM}$
Dy^{3+}	4.2×10^{-4}	Na^{+}	6.3×10^{-4}
Tb^{3+}	3.5×10^{-4}	K^{+}	7.4×10^{-4}
Gd^{3+}	2.2×10^{-3}	Ca^{2+}	6.9×10^{-4}
Lu^{3+}	4.7×10^{-4}	Ba^{2+}	7.8×10^{-4}
Sm^{3+}	2.3×10^{-3}	Pb^{2+}	8.3×10^{-4}
Ho^{3+}	2.0×10^{-3}	Ni^{2+}	4.2×10^{-3}
Tm^{3+}	6.7×10^{-4}	Cd^{2+}	3.6×10^{-3}
Fe^{3+}	3.2×10^{-3}	Co^{2+}	8.4×10^{-4}
Cr^{3+}	2.5×10^{-3}	Zn^{2+}	2.1×10^{-3}

added to a reference solution and the potential is measured. In a separate experiment, interfering ions (B) are successively added to an identical reference solution, until the measured potential matches the one obtained before by adding primary ions. The MPM selectivity coefficient, is then given by the resulting primary ion to interfering ion activity (concentration) ratio, $K^{MPM} = a_A/a_B$. The resulting potentiometric selectivity coefficients are given in Table 2. Table 2 derives the conclusion that the selectivity coefficients for lanthanide, common alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal ions are in the range of 3.5×10^{-4} to 4.2×10^{-3} . The obtained selectivity coefficients revealed that these cations cannot disturb the function of the proposed Yb^{III} membrane sensor.

Analytical applications :

The constructed Yb^{III} sensor was found to work well under the laboratory conditions and can be successfully employed as an indicator electrode in the potentiometric titrations of Yb^{3+} ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) with a standard EDTA solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$). The resulting titration curve is shown in Fig. 5. As can be seen, the amount of Yb^{3+} ions in the solution can be determined with the electrode.

The sensor was used for the determination of Yb^{3+} ions concentration in mixtures of different ions. The results are summarized in Table 3, clearly showing that the recovery of Yb^{3+} ions in all mixtures is acceptable.

Fig. 5. Potentiometric titration curve of 25.0 mL of a $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution of Yb^{3+} with $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ of EDTA.

Table 3. Determination of Yb³⁺ ions in mixtures of different ions

Sr. No.	Composition	Observed content (M)
1.	0.00010 M Yb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Sm(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M La(NO ₃) ₃	0.000097
2.	0.00010 M Yb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Tb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Gd(NO ₃) ₃	0.000103
3.	0.00010 M Yb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Nd(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Er(NO ₃) ₃	0.000102
4.	0.00010 M Yb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Eu(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Ho(NO ₃) ₃	0.000096
5.	0.00010 M Yb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Fe(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Zn(NO ₃) ₂ + 0.001 M NaNO ₃	0.000098
6.	0.00010 M Yb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Al(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Co(NO ₃) ₂ + 0.001 M Ni(NO ₃) ₂	0.000101
7.	0.00010 M Yb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Ca(NO ₃) ₂ + 0.001 M KNO ₃ + 0.001 M Hg(NO ₃) ₂	0.000097
8.	0.00010 M Yb(NO ₃) ₃ + 0.001 M Pb(NO ₃) ₂ + 0.001 M Ba(NO ₃) ₂ + 0.001 M Cr(NO ₃) ₃	0.000104

Conclusion

This work demonstrated that ion selective electrodes based on 1,2-bis(4-chloro)acetophenone oxime ethyl ether (AOEE) exhibits ytterbium selectivity, with very low interference from common alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. The proposed sensor has a very response time (~7 s) and its potential responses are independent of pH in the range 2.6–7.8. The proposed sensor is superior to the existing sensors in terms of response time, lifetime and for actual analysis, and comparable with regard to other parameters such as slope, pH range, concentration range and selectivity.

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